

INTEGRATED AND INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO THE IMPROVEMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS LESSONS

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Abstract: *In this article, we discuss the process of integrating physical and spiritual education in the formation of a harmoniously developed generation.*

Key words: *Classroom, lesson, integration, pedagogy, Innovation.*

Annotatsiya: *Mazkur maqolada barkamol avlodni shakllantirishda jismoniy va ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya integratsiyasini ta'minlash jarayonini tadqiq qilish haqida mulohaza yuritimiz*

Kalit so'zlar: *Sinf, dars, integratsiya, pedagogika, Innovatsiya.*

Аннотация: *В этой статье мы обсуждаем процесс интеграции физического и духовного образования в формировании гармонично развитого поколения.*

Ключевые слова: *Аудитория, урок, интеграция, педагогика, инновации.*

One of the important ideas of the National Personnel Training Program is the need for education to develop in harmony with modern science and technology development, market economy and production. That is why effective use of integration in the development of education is becoming an urgent task.

Integration is the merging of individual parts or elements into a single whole.

The root of the process of integration goes back to the classical pedagogy of the distant past and is represented by the idea of interdisciplinarity, which implies studying the content of the educational material and interpreting nature as a whole.

Undoubtedly, the desire to integrate educational material has a natural and leading character both in the world and in our national pedagogy.

Currently, more attention is paid to the problem of integration in the past and education. However, based on the above considerations, it can be said that integration as a process appears both in basic science and in its branches. Currently, integration in a modern school is considered as a factor that solves pedagogical problems, improves

school activities, increases the potential of the team of pedagogues, and finds optimal ways to influence them.

Innovative pedagogy is a system of knowledge that is currently known as an unofficial science, but is rapidly developing day by day, attracting the attention of experts from all over the world. The team of pedagogues, scientists, who have recognized its educational importance, are critical of the existing traditional pedagogy. Serious opinions are being expressed about this new science, which is being formed and developing these days. Its main task is to reorganize and master the theory of the prevailing educational system based on innovation. Innovative pedagogy is the basis of the ruling theory and solving practical problems. According to the innovators, it is impossible to educate the current generation in this way in the new environment, where classical pedagogical theories are outdated. This is the current situation in the field of pedagogy. In this situation, innovation is very important pedagogy is a system of knowledge, objectivity, appropriateness, consistency are its main characteristics. The main principles of the objective theory must be divided into scientific principles, but it should not be ideological.

Objectivity is the only requirement. Ideology is always the one-sided social interests of one or another social group, which they impose on others as valuable guidance and ideas. The world pedagogic theory has already recognized that the conditions of the educational process are related to the ideas of the people at the top. Education of the growing generations is a very serious matter, and it cannot be left dependent on transient things. As it turns out, one of the main shortcomings of our pedagogical theories, which guide in practice, is to greatly exaggerate the superiority of knowledge and education. got lost.

According to all the signs of the current education and the practice it leads, it is seen that it is in a state of crisis. Any move to break out of this situation is considered innovative, and in this case, they live up to their name. Innovative pedagogy is often called traditional alternative pedagogy. It is impossible not to agree with this opinion, at least according to the simplest concepts, the class, the teacher, the content of the lesson and the textbooks will not disappear. If the pedagogical system is preserved, then we can only talk about its improvement. our strategic way to improve.

It is to adhere to the creation of a didactic and pedagogic system based on the logic of development's concern for its descendants, and this is why folk pedagogy is considered to be a field that teaches nature in a broad sense as the basis of the methodological basis. How children are born depends on no one but their parents, but it is up to each person to develop enough to reach the level of a well-rounded person,

to find their own place in life and activities that they like. z spends his life in accordance with life standards, first of all depends on the school.

- Today, ensuring the integration of physical and spiritual-ethical education in the formation of a student's personality, especially the development of interdisciplinary integration in raising them to be healthy and well-rounded in all aspects, is considered an important socio-pedagogical phenomenon. The solution of this problem serves as a theoretical basis for solving the important pedagogical task facing the continuous education system. Including:
- in-depth study and justification of the process of ensuring the integration of physical and spiritual-ethical education in the formation of a mature generation as a pedagogical problem;
- development of content and pedagogical-psychological features of physical and spiritual-moral education of students;
- to determine the optimal form, methods and means of ensuring the integration of physical and moral education in the formation of the student's personality;
- development of principles and laws of ensuring the integration of physical and spiritual-ethical education in the formation of the student's personality;
- creation of moral and ethical criteria for choosing physical exercises that shape the personality of the perfect generation;
- developing a program to ensure the integration of physical and moral education in the formation of the student's personality;
- to create scientific and methodical recommendations for determining the forms, methods and means of forming spiritual and moral qualities in students through physical education.

Based on the above-mentioned points, it can be said that the research of the process of ensuring the integration of physical and spiritual-moral education in the formation of a mature generation is one of the urgent pedagogical problems waiting for its solution.

REFERENCES

1. Azizxo'jaeva N.N. Pedagogik texnologiya va pedagogik maxorat. Toshkent TDPU. 2003 yil.
2. Azizxo'jaeva N.N. Pedagogik texnologiya va pedagogik mahorat (O'quv qo'llanma). – T.: O'zbekiston yozuvchilar uyushmasi Adabiyot jamg'armasi nashriyoti, 2006 y. – 160 b.
3. R.A.Mavlonova, N.Raxmonqulova “Boshlang'ich ta'limning integratsiyalashgan pedagogikasi” T.: Ili-Ziyo 2009 y.
4. R.A.Mavlonova N.Raxmonqulova “Boshlang'ich ta'lim pedagogikasi innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi. T.: G'.G'ulom 2013 y.
5. Yakhshilikov, Sanjar. (2023). The Impact of a donor's domestic political economy on its policy and practice of development cooperation comparing to the impact of international norms and principles. *Frontline Social Sciences and History Journal*. 03. 32-40. 10.37547/social-fsshj-03-01-05.
6. Xasanov, Anvar. (2017). Физическая культура и спорт как важный аспект в формировании личности. *Форум молодых ученых*. 5. 425-428.
7. Xasanov, Anvar. (2017). Физическая культура-надежда нации. *Форум молодых ученых*. 5. 591.
8. Xasanov, Anvar & Mamanazarova, A. (2022). Website: www.sjird.journalspark.org WRESTLING PREPARATION PROCESS IN SPORTS SCHOOLS. *SPECTRUM Journal of Gender and Children Studies*. 19. 174.
9. Yakhshilikov, Sanjar. (2023). UNAVOIDABLE CLASHES: EXPLORING THE IMPLICATIONS OF A CHINA-RUSSIA ALLIANCE ON GLOBAL GEOPOLITICS. *Austral Brazilian Journal of Strategy & International Relations*. 12. 198-209. 10.22456/2238-6912.131366.
10. Nurmatov, Eldor. (2023). Maqola Jurnal chet el.